

Religious-Based Discrimination Against Muslims in North American and European Prisons: “Comprehensive Discrimination”

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Abstract

This paper attempts to provide insight into the comprehensive religious-based discrimination that Muslims experience in North American and European prisons. The discrimination discussed in this paper is described as “comprehensive” because this paper proves that Muslims experience religious-based discrimination in all prison roles. This included prisoners, guards, chaplains, and even visitors.

Keywords: Religion, Islamic studies, Religious discrimination, Prison, Islam, North America, Europe

Introduction

A prison is a place that provides punishment and rehabilitation for individuals that break the law. It is meant to be a place where individuals reform to become better members of society. However, in order to incarcerate, there is a need to infringe upon the human rights of an inmate. This is problematic, but it becomes particularly problematic when rights relating to religion and religious practice are infringed upon. This is especially true for Muslims who have religious practices that are unique and public, such as wearing certain clothing and engaging in ritual prayer.

Due to the Islamic faith being traditionally understood as an Eastern religion, the question of the status of Muslim prisoners in the West becomes pertinent. Specifically, do Muslims in Western prisons experience discrimination based on their religion? This paper will attempt to argue that Muslims in Western prisons experience discrimination based on their religion as a result of institutional policies and prison employee discretionary actions. In the context of this paper the West will refer to North America and Europe. The United States of America will represent North America and the United Kingdom will represent Europe. These countries were chosen to represent their respective regions due to the large amount of case law, the large amount of scholarly research pertaining to the topic, and the ethnically varied Muslim populations that they individually contain. The thesis statement of this paper will be proven through reference to

journal articles, books, law reviews, legislation, newspaper articles, and legal cases.

North America (The United States of America)

Since the attacks that took place on 9/11, there has been a strain on the relationship between Muslims and American society (Peek, 2010). The attacks have caused Muslims to be seen as outsiders as well as a potential threat to national security (Peek, 2010). This has resulted in discrimination against Muslims in the job market, in schools, and society in general (Peek, 2010). This discrimination has made itself into all facets of American life, including prisons.

Inmates

In 2000, United States Congress passed the *Religious Land Use and Institutionalized Persons Act of 2000* (RLUIPA) which had the goal of protecting prisoners from religious discrimination while in prison (Marcus, 2009). This legislation was introduced due to previous legal cases involving religious discrimination inside of prisons (Marcus, 2009).

Despite the existence of this legislation; Muslim prisoners in the United States continue to experience discrimination based on their religion (Marcus, 2009). Examples of discrimination that Muslim inmates have been subjected to include: refusal to honour the halal diet (Spruel v. Clarke, 2007), refusal to allow prisoners to wear religious clothing

(Abdullah v. Frank, 2007), denial of Qur'an or other religious books (Larry v. Goetz, 2007), interference with observance of religious holidays (Mallory v. Winchester, 2006), prohibitions against facial hair longer than one quarter of an inch (Barnes v. Molett, 2006), and forced participation in Christian religious services (Marcus, 2009). When questioned on why the above-mentioned forms of discrimination were taking place, prison authorities claimed that their restrictions on Muslims prisoners were "a necessary means of ensuring [...] homeland security" (Marcus, 2009). The prison authorities claimed that practicing Islam in prison is a means of radicalization due to the combination of violent prison culture, and religious practice (Marcus, 2009). Therefore "prislam" (Marcus, 2009), or prison Islam, must be quelled for the safety of the nation (Marcus, 2009). It is clear from the information presented above that prison authorities implemented institutional policy, under the guise of national security, that discriminated against Muslims based on their religion.

Custody

Discrimination against Muslims in prison is not unique to those that are incarcerated. There are many cases where individuals are in custody as they have not been convicted of committing a crime, yet they have experienced religion-based discrimination. An example of this is the case surrounding Souhair Khatib. Khatib, a practicing Muslim woman who wore a headscarf, was taken into custody by California police officers (Ammoura, 2013). While in custody she was forced to remove her hijab and remain without it for many hours (Ammoura, 2013). Khatib explained to the prison officers that her religion forbade her from removing her headscarf in front of male non-relatives but the officers threatened to physically take it off of her if she failed to comply (Ammoura, 2013). Khatib reluctantly complied, removed her headscarf, attempted to cover her head with her sweater, and the officers forced her to pull her sweater down (Ammoura, 2013). When probed on why this discrimination occurred, the officers simply stated that it was against the institutions policy to wear the headscarf as Khatib could have hidden something in it (Ammoura, 2013). This case is not unique to Khatib as there have been many similar cases in jails around the United States. It is clear from this explanation that Muslims face discrimination while in custody as a result of institutional policy.

Prison Employees

Muslim prison employees also face discrimination based on their religion while working in prisons. This is clear when one considers cases where Muslim women have been prevented from wearing headscarves while working as prison guards (Duffy, 2009). A notable case involved three Muslim women in Philadelphia who were told they could not wear their headscarves while working in a Philadelphia county prison (Duffy, 2009). The women brought their case to a federal judge who dismissed the case citing the institutions

employee dress-code policy (Duffy, 2009). The county jail had an employee dress-code policy that barred religious clothing in order to maintain "religious neutrality" (Duffy, 2009).

This is not unique to Muslim women. Muslim men have also faced discrimination while working in prisons. Muslim men often grow their beard for religious reasons, and they have also faced discrimination at the hand of their prison employers as a result. One case occurred in New York where two Muslim corrections officers were suspended, and at risk of losing their pensions, for not shaving their beards (Brown, 2019). When questioned on why this discrimination took place; the prison that they worked for cited their employee dress-code policy, which stated that guards must be clean shaven while on duty (Brown, 2019).

Muslim prison chaplains have also reported discrimination while working inside of prisons. Many forms of discrimination have been reported such as demeaning comments by supervisors (Council on American-Islamic Relations, 2019), false accusations of misconduct (Council on American-Islamic Relations, 2019), denial of adjustment for hours (Council on American-Islamic Relations, 2019), and pay-rates that are less than their Christian counterparts (Council on American-Islamic Relations, 2019). It is clear from the above examples that Muslim prison employees experience discrimination based on their religion as a result of institutional policy as well as prison employee discretionary actions.

Prison Visitors

Muslims who make visits to prisons also experience discrimination based on their religion. This is evident when one looks at cases such as Rhouni v. Wisconsin Department of Corrections. In this case Cynthia Rhouni was visiting the Columbia Correctional Institution to visit her incarcerated father. When she arrived for her visit she was told that she needed to remove her headscarf in order to enter the prison pursuant to Wisconsin Administrative Code, Department of Corrections 309, Internal Management Procedures 11, which prohibits visitors from wearing hats or headgear (Abdo, 2008). Rhouni explained that she wore the headscarf for religious reasons and offered to remove it temporarily in the presence of a female guard as proof that she was not concealing anything (Abdo, 2008). However, Rhouni's request was denied, and she was forced to remove her headscarf before she could meet her father (Abdo, 2008).

This case is not unique as there have been other cases such as Sihlangu v. Hollar which considered the issues of barring Muslim women from wearing a headscarf while visiting prisons as well as barring Muslim men who wear skullcaps from visiting prisons (Abdo, 2008). It should also be noted that there have been cases where Muslim women were forced to remove their headscarves to visit a prison while

Mennonite women were permitted to wear their religious bonnets while visiting the same prison (Sihlangu v. Hollar, 1993). There is no shadow of a doubt that Muslims are discriminated against based on their religion when they are visitors to prison. This discrimination is a result of prison policy as well as employee discretion and actions. Now that it has been established that Muslims experience religion-based discrimination in North American prisons, the European context must be examined.

Europe (The United Kingdom)

Europe has an interesting relationship with Muslims as a result of many years of immigration which has created many well-established Muslim communities. Regardless, after consulting the literature, it is clear that Muslims experience discrimination based on religion inside of European prisons.

Inmates

One element that is markedly different from the North American context is that European prison guards are often outwardly prejudice towards Muslim inmates. Prison guards refer to inmates as “Bin Laden” (Beckford, Joly, & Khosrokhavar, 2005), ask if inmates like Bin Laden (Beckford, Joly, & Khosrokhavar, 2005), state to the inmates that “you are all the same” (Beckford, Joly, & Khosrokhavar, 2005), and call Islam “the religion of terrorists” (Beckford, Joly, & Khosrokhavar, 2005). Furthermore, prison guards intentionally disturb Muslim inmates while they are praying (Beckford, Joly, & Khosrokhavar, 2005), and cut off the water supply while Muslim inmates are taking showers (Beckford, Joly, & Khosrokhavar, 2005). It has also been reported that prison guards require Muslim prisoners to stand naked, in the view of prison officers, for up to 15 minutes after a strip search (Beckford, Joly, & Khosrokhavar, 2005). These are all examples of religious-based discrimination as a result of prison employee discretionary actions.

The prison institution, through institutional policy, also engages in discrimination against Muslim inmates based on religion. Examples of this include forcing inmates to rely on charitable donations from outside of the prison to purchase prayer mats (Beckford, Joly, & Khosrokhavar, 2005), preventing Muslim inmates from attending family funerals while Christian inmates are allowed (Cairns, 2015), failing to provide adequate facilities for ritual ablutions (Beckford, Joly, & Khosrokhavar, 2005), and failing to provide adequate facilities for congregational prayer (Cairns, 2015).

The issue of failing to provide adequate facilities for congregational prayer is controversial as worship is the essence of religion in Islam (Soliman, 2015). In some prisons there are facilities offered for congregational prayer, but they are much too small. An example of this is a prison in the United Kingdom where the congregational prayer facility can accommodate approximately 35 people while the amount of inmates that regularly attend the prayer is 50 (Cairns, 2015).

In other prisons, there are no facilities for congregational prayer and inmates are forced to pray in “classrooms, the Chaplains’ office, the dining room, the television room, the adjudication room, and the barber shop” (Joly, 2007).

Muslim inmates are also not being given access to halal food which is in accordance to their religiously mandated diet (Cairns, 2015). Even when halal food is supposedly offered, it has been uncovered that prison administration often lie, and simply relabel food from non-halal sources as halal (Joly, 2007).

Prison Employees

Muslim employees also face discrimination based on their religion in European prisons. This is seen predominantly with Muslim chaplains not being treated with respect or as equals (Cairns, 2015). Muslim chaplains indicate that they experience overt racism from their colleagues and other staff within the prison facility (Beckford, Joly, & Khosrokhavar, 2005). There were also more subtle forms of discrimination such as Muslim chaplains not being given keys to the prison cells while Christian chaplains were given keys (Beckford, Joly, & Khosrokhavar, 2005), lack of staff co-operating with Muslim chaplains (Beckford, Joly, & Khosrokhavar, 2005), Muslim chaplains “being treated as uncooperative figures of suspicion rather than colleagues by prison staff” (Joly, 2007), open hostility against Muslim Chaplains (Beckford, Joly, & Khosrokhavar, 2005), failure to make timely salary payments to Muslim Chaplains (Beckford, Joly, & Khosrokhavar, 2005), and demeaning behaviour towards Muslim Chaplains (Beckford, Joly, & Khosrokhavar, 2005). These are all clear examples of religion-based discrimination as a result of prison employee discretionary actions.

There was also a serious lack of training for Muslim Chaplains when compared to that of Christian chaplains (Beckford, Joly, & Khosrokhavar, 2005). This issue is compounded by the fact that there is a shortage of Muslim Chaplains. For each Muslim chaplain in British prisons there are approximately five Christian chaplains; even though Muslims outnumber Christians in the prison system (Beckford, Joly, & Khosrokhavar, 2005). The shortage puts Muslim inmates at risk of radicalization. This is due to the fact that in prison there are Muslims who preach radical ideologies. Ideally these ideologies would be refuted by Muslim chaplains who have an formal education in Islam, but due to the shortage, they do not have this opportunity (Beckford, Joly, & Khosrokhavar, 2005). This is a clear example of religion-based discrimination as a result of institution policy, or lack thereof, which failed to provide an adequate number of Muslim chaplains.

Conclusion

Through an analysis of journal articles, books, law reviews, legislation, newspaper articles, and legal cases it has been proven that Muslims experience religion-based discriminated in Western prisons. This was done through an analysis of the

United States of America and the United Kingdom as representatives for North America and Europe respectively. It was shown that Muslims of all roles, from inmate to employee, experienced religion-based-discrimination as a result of institutional policies and prison employee discretionary actions.

The findings of this paper are problematic due to the fact that legislation currently exists that are supposed to prevent religious-based discrimination. In the North American context, the legislation that exists is the first Amendment right under the United States Constitution which protects freedom of religion, and the RLUIPA which protects prisoners from religious discrimination while in prison. In Europe the legislation that exists is article 9 of the European Convention on Human Rights which protects freedom of religion. Why does discrimination still take place when there is legislation to prevent it? The answer is that the institutions that are meant to be enforcing the law, namely prisons and prison authorities, simply fail to follow the law when it comes to dealing with Muslims in prison. The findings of this paper are therefore important because they expose the double standard that exists in the criminal justice system. The prisons claim that they enforce the law when they are not even following the law in the first place. Not only are they not following the law; they are transgressing against it.

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